

Lipid Bilayer Membrane Technologies: Single-molecule Studies of DNA Sequencing by using Membrane Nanopores

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Abstract:

Nanopores based on α -hemolysin and MspA represent attractive sensing platforms due to easy production and operation with relatively low background noise. Such characteristics make them highly favorable for sequencing nucleic acids. Artificial lipid bilayer membranes, also referred to as black lipid membranes, in conjunction with membrane nanopores, can be applied to both the detection and highly efficient sequencing of DNA on a single-molecule level. However, the inherently weak physical properties of the membrane have impeded progress in these areas. Current issues impeding the ultimate recognition of the artificial lipid bilayer as a viable platform for detection and sequencing of DNA include membrane stability, lifespan, and automation. This review (with 107 references) highlights attempts to improve the attributes of the artificial lipid bilayer membrane starting with an overview on the present state and limitations. The first, main section covers lipid bilayer membranes (BLM) in general. The following section reviews the various kinds of lipid bilayer membrane platforms with subsections on polymer membranes, solid-supported membranes, hydrogel-encapsulated membranes, shippable and storable membrane platforms, and droplet interface bilayers. A further section covers engineered biological nanopore sensor applications using BLMs with subsections offering a comparative view of different DNA sequencing methods, a detailed look at DNA Sequencing by synthesis using alpha-hemolysin nanopores, sequencing by synthesis using the MspA nanopore and quadromer map, and on limitations of sequencing based on synthesis technology. We present an outlook at the end that discusses current research trends on single-molecule sequencing to highlight the significance of this technology and its potential in the medical and environmental fields.

Keywords: black lipid membrane, membrane platform, supported membrane, hydrogel-encapsulated membrane, droplet interface bilayer, biomimetic, biological nanopore, alpha-hemolysin, MspA, sequencing by synthesis

1. Overview

The four major molecular building blocks that compose cells are lipids, carbohydrates, proteins, and nucleic acids. [1] Of these building blocks, lipids are an essential constituent of the cell membrane, the barrier that encapsulates the fundamental unit of life. The lipids in the membrane are arranged in two apposed sheets known as the lipid bilayer, which serves as a permeable barrier to most water-soluble molecules. [2] Ion channels and other transmembrane proteins housed in this bilayer facilitate different cell functions and give membranes their individual characteristics. [2] Thus, the characterization of these proteins and their functions is crucial to research on and possible manipulation of their functions for clinical and life science applications.[3] A typical method for the characterization of functional membrane proteins is the patch clamp technique, [4] which is often used to study physiological functions, kinetics, and drug responses of single or multiple ion channels simultaneously. [4] The patch clamp technique is a powerful tool for interpreting electrophysiological phenomena, especially in excitable cells such as muscle fibers and neurons. [5] Many researchers rely on this technique, and it is considered the gold standard for studying ion channels. However, limitations of the traditional patch clamp technique arise from its low current resolution and highly challenging execution. [4]

Alternatively, artificially created lipid bilayer membranes can provide a biological environment in which ion channels and other transmembrane proteins can be incorporated *ex vivo* and can be studied for an extended duration in a cost-effective manner. Ever since the first artificial lipid bilayer membrane was created *ex vivo* by Muller et al. in the early 1960s, [6] artificially constructed model membranes have been

extensively used to elucidate the functions of transmembrane proteins, [7-9] to study membrane biophysics, [10-14] and to create protein-based sensors. [15-19] Channel proteins integrated into a model membrane display their unique conducting characteristics from the ionic current passing through their pores. Electrical measurements made through protein pores show physical changes in protein structure, as well as the presence of any small molecules blocking the conducting pathway through the protein. [20-22] Such measurements are essential to understanding the proteins' biological functions, and they may serve as a basis for highly specific sensors capable of chemical detection, [16] or potentially for sequencing DNA at the single-molecule level. [23,24]

Although the direct electrical measurement of channel conductance is a very powerful technique, the artificial lipid bilayer membrane in this system has critical drawbacks that have precluded it from being used more frequently. For example, artificial lipid bilayers have a short lifespan, with the typical bilayer remaining viable for only a few hours. Additionally, the membrane is somewhat fragile, collapsing under mechanical or electrical stress, and is limited to use with organic solvent. [3] Regardless, the lipid bilayer membrane remains an attractive bio sensing platform. Consequently, a model membrane system has been the subject of significant interest. Research to develop a reliable biomimetic membrane system with improved stability and longevity is ongoing.

Previously studied methods used to enhance mechanical stability and durability have included the use of solid supports to stabilize the membrane structure, [25,26] as well as porous material [27] and soft matter, such as hydrogels and polymeric matrices. [26,25,28,29] One such method involves creating a hydrogel-encapsulated and

conjugated membrane, thus ultimately resulting in a significantly increased lifespan and enhanced mechanical stability. [30-33] The head groups of the lipid molecules are modified to contain vinyl groups, which can be crosslinked with dimethacrylate groups at the end of hydrogel monomers, thereby increasing the lifespan of the membrane to approximately 11 days. Hydrogel encapsulation provides a platform for stochastic sensing, thus enabling a rapid and reliable response and an overall cost-effective sensor. [16] The portability of the lipid bilayer membrane has been addressed with the integration of the hydrogel-encapsulated membrane within microchips, thereby resulting in a lipid bilayer membrane that is robust enough to ship commercially. [34,35] Hydrogel encapsulation methods are a particularly promising platform when physically robust membranes integrated with functional proteins, such as sensors and ion- or molecule-selective filters, are required. [36] Aside from hydrogels, an alternate artificial lipid bilayer called the droplet interface bilayer, shows promise in providing the strength and durability necessary to make lipid bilayers a commonly used platform in the laboratory for ion characterization and countless other applications. [37]

In this review, we focus on the artificial lipid bilayer membrane and provide a foundation for the research developments that facilitated its production. We give examples of the early use of hydrogels for membrane stabilization and discuss the applications of state-of-the-art biomimetic membrane technologies that use hydrogels. Finally, we review the lipid bilayer in use as a biosensor through the integration of biological nanopores. We also explore some novel methods of single-molecule-level DNA sequencing using protein nanopores embedded in artificial lipid bilayers with a focus on sequencing by synthesis (SBS) technique, which is an emerging, viable method for DNA

sequencing with nanopores. Additionally, we explore potential future directions and applications for this technology as well as current limitations and obstacles to overcome.

2. Lipid bilayer membranes (BLM)

In 1962, Mueller et al. reported a method of creating the first *in vitro* reconstituted cell membrane. [6] A typical apparatus for creating membranes in which to embed channel proteins consists of two chambers that are divided by an insulating partition with a small orifice, hundreds of micrometers in diameter. The lipid bilayer membrane is spread across this orifice, and when a solvent containing lipids is spread across a small aperture, the free lipids in solution self-assemble to form a lipid bilayer. However, work must first be done to ensure the formation of the bilayer, because the bulk solution of lipids is at a lower free energy state than at the thin bilayer. Therefore, this system is considered to be in a metastable equilibrium state. [38] Although several forces influence lipid bilayer formation, [39] the two main forces are Laplace pressure and van der Waals interactions. The hydrophobicity of the substrate, usually Teflon, Kel-F, or polyethylene, induces curvature within the annulus, which consists of organic solvent and lipids. The curvature at the Plateau-Gibbs border generates a pressure difference, ΔP , which is related to the radius of curvature R and the interfacial tension γ [39]:

$$\Delta P = 2\gamma / R$$

The pressure differential created by the curvature drives the bulk solution from the middle of the opening to the edge. As sufficient solvent is removed from the middle of the opening, owing to the Laplace pressure, the initially thick solvent layer thins and forms a film several tens of nanometers (nm) thick. At this point, a “zipping” process between the

two monolayers begins, driven by van der Waals interactions between the two hydrophobic layers of lipid molecules, thus bringing them into contact and forming a bilayer membrane (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Schematic illustration of membrane formation. (A) P_{out} is greater than P_{in} , thus making the solvent flow to the edge. (B) Van der Waals interactions between the two monolayers bring them into contact and initiate a zipping process to create a bilayer membrane. (C) A lipid bilayer membrane is formed after completion of the zipping process.

This membrane is typically called a black lipid bilayer membrane (BLM) because of its optical properties when observed under a microscope. The membrane has a thickness of 3~5 nm and reflects light paths 180 ° out of phase, thus resulting in destructive interference and making the lipid bilayer appear black. Other common names for this type of membrane are a planar membrane, planar lipid membrane (PLM), and lipid bilayer membrane.

By applying the same principle, several variations of membrane reconstitution methods have been introduced. The basic concept of a folded bilayer was first established by Takagi et al. [40] and was refined by Montal and Mueller. [41] Their modification to the membrane consisted of the bilayer being created across an aperture by folding two monolayers spread along an air/water interface. This method was further studied and

adopted by Pattus et al. [42] and Schindler et al. [43,44], who introduced liposomes to spread monolayers along the interface. The fundamental concept of this method was influenced by studies by Eriksson, Phillips and Tajima, describing the equilibrium between monolayers and liposomes at the air/water interface. [45-47]

A lipid bilayer membrane is theoretically well suited for studying ion channels and membrane science. However, a freestanding lipid bilayer membrane is fragile and has a short lifespan, thereby precluding some practical applications. Although there has been increasing demand for a robust and reliable membrane system, significant technological advances to stabilize the lipid bilayer membrane have not been made during the past few decades. As a result, several modifications to the method and advanced techniques have been reported to date for the creation of stable biomimetic membranes. Of those techniques, hydrogel encapsulation is particularly attractive because it does not interfere with electrical measurement the transport of analytes through channel proteins. Furthermore, hydrogel encapsulation provides efficient physical support to the membrane structure, and thus prolongs the lipid bilayer membrane lifespan and enhances its durability.

3. Lipid Bilayer Membrane Platforms

Although the artificial lipid bilayer membrane provides very suitable conditions for *ex vivo* function of membrane proteins, it has limited applications due to the fragility of the freestanding lipid bilayer. Table 1 shows various approaches for stabilizing the membrane and increasing its viability both in the laboratory setting and for commercial use. In this section, we focus on five such methods: polymer membranes, solid supported

membranes, hydrogel-encapsulated membranes, shippable and storable membrane platforms, and droplet interface bilayers.

Membrane Platform	Advantages	Limitations	References
Polymer Membranes	Creates a biomimetic environment ideal for biological applications	Not as stable and robust as other platforms	[48-51]
Solid Supported Membranes	Offers exceptional strength and stability	Structural and functional parameters vary	[52-54]
Hydrogel Encapsulated Membranes	Provides physical support while still allowing ion transfer	Reduced lipid diffusivity due to crosslinked hydrogel matrix	[28,32,30,31,33]
Shippable and Storable Membranes	Robust enough to transport and store commercially	Membrane formation time varies	[34,55]
Droplet Interface Bilayer membranes	Robust and able to measure scarce analytes or rapidly measure transmembrane diffusion; automated	Throughput and efficiency can be enhanced	[37]

Table 1 List summarizing lipid bilayer membrane platforms with their advantages and limitations

3.1 Polymer Membranes and Solid-Supported Membranes

Countless efforts have been made to ameliorate the inherent fragility of artificial membranes, including the use of robust synthetic polymers in place of the lipids and mechanical supports to strengthen the membrane structure. Nardin et al. first explored the feasibility of a biomimetic membrane by using ABA block copolymers as alternative materials to the lipids previously used in the construction of artificial bilayers. [51,48-50] The polymer membrane is composed of long amphiphilic blocks that may adhere to neighboring molecules more tightly than would a lipid molecule, thus resulting in stronger molecular affinity. Additionally, the block copolymers used in this work have head groups

that can be crosslinked at both ends of each molecule to create a strong mesh-like network. [51]

Figure 2 Schematic of hydrophilic polymer molecules within the shell of a vesicle. Shorter block-length polymers segregate toward the inside, and the longer chains move towards the outside.

The primary aim of this experiment was to demonstrate that a membrane made of synthetic polymers can provide a biological environment and can serve as a platform in which membrane proteins can properly function. To demonstrate the feasibility of use of the polymer membrane as a biomimetic platform, bacterial outer membrane protein A and other membrane proteins were incorporated into the Nardin polymer membrane and were shown to work properly. More interestingly, the head group crosslinked polymer membrane did not interrupt the functionality of the membrane proteins tested, [48-51] even though the fluidity of the membrane is a key factor in determining the function of membrane proteins and increased crosslinking generally results in a less fluid bilayer membrane. It was hypothesized that the crosslinked membranes may extend the lifetime of the membrane and offer better stability. However, longevity and mechanical stability were not demonstrated. Subsequent work with the polymer membrane focused on electrical activities of various membrane proteins, including α -hemolysin (α HL) and outer

membrane protein G, as well as peptides such as alamethicin and gramicidin.[56] The proteins incorporated into the polymer membranes also function as they did in the lipid bilayer membrane. [56-58] However, the membrane stability, longevity, and whether polymer membranes can be used as robust biomimetic membrane platforms remain to be addressed.

Frequently used techniques to stabilize a lipid bilayer membrane rely on various types of solid supports, including metallic, silicon, and polymer matrices. [52] Membranes form on the solid support either by conjugation, or simply by physical affinity. Polymers conjugated with the membrane decrease membrane-substrate interactions and create a cushion that mimics the cytoskeleton of the cell. [53] The use of molecular scaffolds or tethers inside and outside the bilayer have been shown to form a stabilizing matrix that maintains bilayer fluidity while improving stability. [54,53] Solid supported membranes have made substantial advancements in the use of lipid bilayers for many practical platforms, thus making them a very useful tool for studying membrane physics and protein-lipid interactions. [52] An interesting application of the supported bilayer is a bio sensing platform, first suggested by Cornell et al., in which a recognition event switches the conductance of a population of molecular ion channels in a way that mimics sensory functions. [59]

Despite the potential of polymer and solid support bilayers to meet the structural needs of high-throughput bio sensing platforms, the methods introduce additional obstacles for researchers to overcome when considering them sensors. The strength and stability provided by the solid supports are crucial to making long-term direct current (DC) measurements. DC measurements are often used to probe ion channel activities and

molecular interactions at the single molecule level. Therefore, long-term DC measurements are critical for sensing platforms. However, the formation of the bilayers with solid supports requires the membrane to have intimate contact with a solid surface, thus resulting in a small reservoir of electrolyte solution. Consequently, long-term DC measurements are limited, excluding many important sensing applications and making solid supported membranes impractical for bio sensing applications. Additionally, the thickness of the sub-membrane polymer reservoir depends on both the polydispersity of the polymer used and its swelling behavior upon hydration. [53] Both factors are difficult to control with absolute precision. Therefore, the resulting bilayers have often been shown to contain holes and defects, thus making polymer supported bilayers less favorable for use as bio sensing platforms. [60,61]

3.2 Hydrogel-Encapsulated Membranes

Hydrogel supports have been used to address the durability drawbacks of the artificial lipid bilayer membrane. Hydrogels provide physical support for the lipid bilayer while still allowing ion transport. Early work with hydrogels employed a precast gel matrix. Costello et al. have demonstrated a new technique that protects a freestanding lipid bilayer from both mechanical disturbance and drying out. [28] They measured the conductance and capacitance of the membrane for approximately three weeks, showing that the electrical seal remained intact. In this work, however, ion channel activity was not shown during the measurement period. In the same year, Ide et al. developed a similar method for stabilizing a freestanding lipid bilayer by using a hydrogel support. In this method, a slab of precast hydrogel is used to support a lipid bilayer structure

mechanically. [29] Both studies have successfully used precast hydrogels to mechanically support the lipid bilayer.

Figure 3 When a hydrogel precursor (A.) crosslinks with the head group of a modified lipid (B) while the lipids are present in a bilayer, the bilayer becomes covalently linked to the surrounding hydrogel matrix (C).

Later work with hydrogels by Jeon et al. demonstrated an *in-situ* hydrogel encapsulation method to mitigate the remaining drawbacks of conventional systems. In this work, a lipid bilayer was formed in the presence of an electrolyte solution containing a hydrogel precursor solution. The hydrogel precursor solution was composed of PEG-1000-DMA (polyethyleneglycol-1000-dimethylmethacrylate) and the photo initiator Irgacure 2959. The solution was then polymerized into a hydrogel after UV illumination. The major advantage of this method is that the hydrogels engage in intimate contact with

the membrane, thus resulting in exceptional stability whereas the transport of water and ions is not attenuated. [31,32,62,30] Jeon et al. first demonstrated that positional hydrogel encapsulation increases longevity and mechanical stability. Later work with hydrogels reports on head group-modified lipids that can be conjugated to the adjacent hydrogels. The crosslinks between the membrane and hydrogel matrix is achieved after UV polymerization, thus increasing the lifespan and durability of the membrane. Although the diffusivity of lipid molecules within the membrane is decreased because of the crosslinked lipid molecules, the functionality of membrane proteins tested remained unchanged.

For sensing applications, the hydrogel matrix can be a major issue in analyte transport. However, subsequent work by Shim et al. and Kang et al. [34,35] using a hydrogel-encapsulated membrane (HEM), has demonstrated the stochastic sensing of small molecules, thus showing that the HEM is a feasible and robust platform for sensor applications. Because of the versatility and success of hydrogels applied to the lipid bilayer, additional lipid bilayer platforms with hydrogels have been developed. One such biomimetic membrane array is shown in Ibragimova et al., who have used poly (ethylene glycol)-di(meth)acrylate networks to improve crosslinking at room temperature. [63] This report is significant because the biomimetic protein matrix generally degrades at higher temperatures and therefore, the liquid and cross-linkable characteristics at room temperature increase the viability of the array. [63]

3.3 Shippable and Storable Membrane Platforms

The fragile nature of the suspended bilayer structure has excluded it from being used in commercial applications, such as diagnostic tools and small molecule detectors.

To use the membrane technology in a practical manner, the ability to be shipped and stored reliably is crucial. To increase the longevity and portability of membranes, hydrogel-encapsulation has been further explored by researchers who used newly designed chips. [34,35] Shim and coworkers have reported that a membrane made on a modular chip can be carried out of the laboratory only when handled with care. The membrane was shown to withstand transport over short distances. However, shifting in position and the possible rearrangement of chips during transport over long distances contribute to membrane damage. Improved mechanical stability has been demonstrated by Kang et al., who found that a membrane made in a chip can remain intact on a platform shaker at rotational speeds of 120 rpm. They also found that the bilayer membranes in this chip can be stored in a 4 °C refrigerator and that the membranes remained intact for up to three weeks.[34] Although this work with hydrogel stabilization is promising, the transport and storage capabilities are still limited, and the membranes must be handled with care. To be commercially viable for shipping, new advances in membranes or in their packaging will be needed to address their inherent fragility.

One incentive for developing a structurally robust artificial lipid bilayer membrane is the potential development of a high-throughput membrane system. High-throughput systems are necessary to advance the development of membrane technologies in the pharmaceutical field. Various groups have patterned supported bilayers and measured them optically in parallel. [64,65] Although these systems can be measured in parallel, the membrane formation technique does not lend itself to automation as a result of the stringent conditions necessary for bilayer formation and the high degree of operator training required. Other groups have attempted to automate the membrane formation

process using microfluidics. [66-68] These methods have not yet demonstrated full automation and still require a technician to operate the pumps and valves for membrane formation.

In the context of studying cellular function, many groups have utilized the mechanisms of the long-term preservation of living cells, tissues, and organs. Well-known techniques to enhance cell, tissue, or organ stability and longevity include cryopreservation, hypothermic and dry-state preservation. [69-71] Similarly, to keep the lipid bilayer membrane intact for commercial transport, freezing and freeze-drying techniques would be favorable options for applications that require resistance to mechanical perturbation. Preserving a freestanding membrane has been beyond the scope of common techniques, because freeze-drying a 5 nm thick membrane is not a trivial problem. In this case, the in-depth experience of biological cell preservation does not seamlessly extend to an artificial membrane system. However, the ability to freeze artificial membranes would have numerous advantages in terms of transportability and storage, thus widening their applicability, and hence is worth exploring further. A technique has been devised to make a membrane precursor by freezing a solvent mixture containing lipid molecules before the spontaneous process of thinning into a bilayer. The membrane precursor contains a mixture of solvents, including hexadecane, which has a relatively high melting temperature. Membranes can then be created effortlessly and automatically by bringing the frozen membrane precursor to room temperature. Figure 4 shows that once the membrane precursor solution is brought to room temperature, it thaws within a few minutes and then undergoes thinning, thereby creating a lipid bilayer membrane. The membrane precursor can be frozen and maintained in that state

indefinitely, thus suggesting that the membrane can be stored and transported without any concern. In fact, the precursor has already been shown to withstand harsh conditions of shipment via a commercial carrier. [72,73]

Figure 4 Schematic diagram of frozen Membrane Precursor with Expedited Self-assembly (MPES) formation. Membrane precursors can be frozen indefinitely or thawed at room temperature, at which time lipid bilayer formation occurs.[72]

The ability to store and transport this membrane platform would significantly decrease the skill level needed to handle the product, to the point that the process can even be automated. This technique of using a frozen membrane precursor applies to several practical lipid bilayer platforms, including bio sensing, ion channel studies and single-molecule DNA sequencing. Technology using frozen membrane precursors is now commercially available. With further optimization and technological development, we envision a practical and easy-to-use ion channel system, wherein membranes are ordered from a central location and are shipped to various scientific and industrial centers

around the world for various applications. Although this frozen membrane precursor is a significant advancement, a few problems remain. In work by Jeon, et al., the membrane formation step, called "thinning-out," has been reported to vary from 30 minutes to several hours. Important factors determining the membrane thinning time include the amount of solvent deposited in the aperture, the geometry and surface property of the opening, and the lipid concentration. [55] Later work by Ryu et al. sought to improve the thinning-out time and successfully produced consistent membrane formation in less than an hour by introducing polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS), which absorbs organic solvent, to replace the conventional Teflon film. [72,73]

3.4 Droplet Interface Bilayers (DIBs)

Figure 5 Conceptual diagram of lipid bilayer formation by bringing two lipid monolayers into contact. Two aqueous droplets in organic solution containing lipid molecules are brought together, and a bilayer forms.[74]

Droplet Interface Bilayers (DIBs) are a family of lipid bilayers that differ slightly from the BLM and that are particularly useful for technological applications. Initially introduced by Tsofina et al. [75], an aqueous droplet is first placed in oil, and the lipids then self-

assemble at the water/oil interface to create a monolayer. [37] The process is then repeated with a second aqueous droplet, and this is followed by joining with the previous monolayer to form a lipid bilayer. DIBs are similar in many ways to conventional artificial bilayers in terms of their compatibility with various lipids, although they possess several key advantages. These advantages include their ability to measure scarce analytes or rapidly measure transmembrane diffusion. They also show durability to withstand movement of the droplet, the ability to be measured over several days, portability, and an overall robust and long lifespan. [37] Ion channels from organisms including bacteria and humans have been measured in DIBs, and they have demonstrated no significant differences compared with conventional bilayers. [37] Hence, DIBs may be viable in platforms in which BLM have been commonly used. They are especially appealing for use in microfluidic devices, high-throughput chips and arrays, and automated motion control hardware. [37]

Over forty years after their first work was reported in 1965, Funakoshi et al. reinvented their membrane formation technique. Figure 5 illustrates this renovated technique, which uses two aqueous droplets in organic solvent containing lipid molecules. [74] However, this membrane formation was not automated. Malmstadt et al. have incorporated a similar principle but have explored and successfully implemented automated lipid bilayer formation by using a monolayer contacting method. [67] The lipid bilayer is created in a microfluidic device made of PDMS via contact between two lipid monolayers. Lipid molecules dissolved in the organic phase are self-assembled along the aqueous and organic interface. After the extraction of the organic phase located between the two monolayers, a lipid bilayer is automatically created. Moreover, the most notable

outcome of the monolayer contacting method is that it enables the creation of an asymmetric bilayer in a controlled manner.

The monolayer contacting method is currently the most commonly used method for the creation of a lipid bilayer, because of the ease of formation and the versatility of the membrane platform. Because monolayer contact has been shown to be a technique that is compatible with automated lipid bilayer formation, many attempts have been made to increase its throughput and efficiency for full automation. [76,77] One example is in the work performed by Acharya et al., who have developed an automatable, parallelizable droplet bilayer. [78] An agarose hydrogel droplet composed the upper aqueous solution of the lipid membrane environment was attached to a movable electrode. Once encapsulated in the hydrogel, the membrane was able to withstand large flow speeds, thus making it compatible with high-throughput parallel fluid handling hardware. [78] In another example, Kawano et al. expanded on the notion of a portable bilayer membrane and applied this technology to bio sensing in an outdoor environment. [79] Figure 6 includes a schematic of Kawano's membrane, which was formed via the monolayer contact of two droplets in a double-well chip.

Figure 6 (a) Schematic of droplet contact method. (b) Illustration of double-well chip used for ion channel measurement. (c) Schematic of α -hemolysin nanopore integrated into a lipid bilayer recording ion passing through the channel. (d) Photograph of a Kawano complete portable system.[79]

Portability was demonstrated by using a handheld amplifier and laptop computer that can be easily transported between various locations. The noise was decreased by wiring Ag/AgCl electrodes underneath the double well instead of using traditional electrode placement directly in the buffer. The membrane was integrated with the α -hemolysin nanopore, and successful single ion channel activity was recorded on the summit of Mt. Fuji as a proof of concept. [79] Such advancements may pave the way for various environmental measurements, including the nanofiltration of water, the quantification of deleterious gases, and the detection of chemical agent odors in nature. [79]

4. Engineered Nanopore Sensor Applications using the Lipid Bilayer Platform

Nanopore technology is especially attractive for the application of DNA sequencing. DNA sequencing has been transformed over the past decade through the

commercialization of new and relatively inexpensive short sequence reading technology. [80] However, although technology has improved sequence throughput and has decreased its cost, full genome analysis still requires several days and thousands of dollars to complete. [81,82] For example, optical techniques for sequencing have been developed and commercialized with remarkable success, yet these techniques require expensive instrumentation and fluorescently tagged nucleotides. [83,84] Biological and solid-state nanopores offer a low-cost alternative that is driving the advancement of DNA sequencing even further. Nanopore sequencing devices are capable of the single-molecule detection of a wide variety of analytes of medical interest, ranging from small molecules to post-translationally modified proteins. Two widely used biological nanopore proteins used in conjunction with the artificial lipid bilayer are α HL and MspA. Both α HL and MspA nanopores are used in a variety of methods of single-molecule DNA detection, including stochastic sensing, in which a single nanopore is inserted into a lipid bilayer and the ionic current driven through it is monitored. [80,85] Other methods include exonuclease-based sequencing, in which nucleotides are enzymatically cleaved from the DNA and are monitored as they pass through the nanopore, [86] and sequencing by synthesis, in which identifiable polymer tags are attached to nucleotides and are registered in nanopores during enzyme-catalyzed DNA synthesis. [87] A list of common methods for nanopore DNA sequencing is provided in Table 2.

Sequencing Method	Advantages	Limitations	References
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Stochastic Sensing	Low cost; Various analytes can be recognized by one detection element	Low accuracy and high signal noise	[85,80,48-51]
Exonuclease Based Sequencing	Reliably distinguish nucleotide bases without need for polymer labeling	Exonuclease required to have affinity to protein nanopore; does not read intact DNA (not repeatable with same strand)	[86,88]
Sequencing by Synthesis	Ability to discriminate DNA on single molecule level using bio nanopores	Requires a reference sequence for accurate alignment; Not yet optimized	[89,87]
Two-Dimensional Sequencing using solid state nanopores [90]	Membrane thickness comparable to distance between ssDNA nucleotide base	Temporal resolution must be improved; cannot determine orientation of nucleotide, signal noise	[90]

Table 2 A comprehensive list of nanopore based sequencing methods with advantages and limitations.

Nanopore sequencing offers the promise of rapidly sequencing long single molecules of DNA, amplification-free sample preparation, and direct detection of epigenetic modifications including base methylation. [85] Nanopore sensors are highly versatile platforms for the rapid, label-free electrical detection and analysis of single molecules. Biological nanopores, in particular, are easily fabricated, modifiable, and enable repeatable and reliable electrical current measurements because they generally do not vary in size. [37] α HL is an exotoxin secreted by the bacterium *Staphylococcus aureus*. This nanopore structure remains functionally stable at temperatures close to 100 °C within a wide pH range, [91] and because of its proximity in size to single-stranded DNA molecules, [91] α HL can discriminate among single nucleotides by using ionic current inside the nanopore. MspA is derived from *Mycobacterium smegmatis* and is often used in four nucleotide base sequencing methods. [91] Its ability to withstand extreme experimental conditions, including changes in pH and high experimental temperatures,

[91] is comparable to that of α HL. However, its dimensions are smaller and narrower than those of α HL, [91] thus resulting in improved resolution for single-strand DNA sequencing.

Nanopore sequencing methods are not free of limitations. For example, nanopore DNA sequencing is plagued by ultrafast translocation speeds that do not allow for distinguishable base discrimination. [92] Also, the operator is limited by the thickness of the membrane in which the nanopore resides, often resulting in increased electrical noise and lower resolution. [92]

4.1 Sequencing by Synthesis

Sequencing by synthesis is a technique in single-molecule DNA sequencing in which polymer tags are attached to nucleotides and registered in nanopores during DNA synthesis. The basic principle underlying this technique is that each nucleotide is tagged with a polymer, such as PEG, incorporated into the translocating DNA strand during the polymerase reaction. [87] The polymerase attached to the pore tightly binds the DNA template and primer, thus completing a single structure that integrates itself into a lipid bilayer configured for monitoring transmembrane conductance and ready for sequencing DNA.[89] When each complementary tagged nucleotide binds the polymerase–primer–template complex, its tag is released in response to applied voltage of typically ~100 mV [89], and then it enters the nanopore in the order of release. [89,87] This process produces a unique ionic current blockade signature based on the tags' distinct chemical structures, thereby determining the DNA sequence electronically at the single-molecule level with single-base resolution. [87] A basic schematic of this process is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7 Schematic of single-molecule DNA sequencing by a nanopore with phosphate-tagged nucleotides. Each of the four nucleotides carries a different tag, which is released into the nanopore one at a time and produce a unique current blockade signature. A large array of such nanopores can allow for highly parallel high-throughput DNA sequencing. [87]

The DNA polymerases of *Escherichia coli* (Klenow fragment) [93-95] and the bacteriophages T7 [93] and phi29 [96,97] have been studied as molecular motors to control the movement of DNA in single nucleotide steps through α HL. In contrast to the Klenow fragment and T7 DNAP, phi29 DNAP can synthesize very long stretches of DNA (>70 kb) along a single template strand and can synthesize under loads of up to ~37 pN, [98] which are sufficient to counteract the electrophoretic force needed to drive DNA through the pore. In a technique reported in Cherf et al., phi29 DNAP is bound to a DNA template and a 'blocking oligomer' that prevents the extension and excision of a primer annealed at the 3' end of the template. The single-stranded end of this phi29 DNAP-DNA

complex is drawn into the nanopore until the DNAP rests on the pore's entrance. The force on the template strand, estimated to be ~10 pN, causes the blocking oligomer to 'unzip' 3' to 5', thus exposing the extendable 3' end of the primer and allowing synthesis to start. [96] Below, we present examples of SBS DNA sequencing by using phi29 DNAP for translocation through biological nanopores incorporated into the lipid bilayer.

4.1.1 DNA sequencing by synthesis using the α HL nanopore

Early work performed by Fuller et al. described an SBS strategy that accurately distinguishes four bases by electronically detecting and differentiating four different polymer tags attached to the 5'-phosphate of the nucleotides during their incorporation into a growing DNA strand catalyzed by DNA polymerase. Figure 8 depicts the α HL nanopore–polymerase sequencing engine that was used, in which a single phi29 DNA polymerase molecule was covalently attached to α HL. This nanopore SBS approach has the advantage of using synthetic polymer tags attached to the nucleotides that are designed specifically to produce unique and readily distinguishable ionic current blockade signatures for sequence determination. [87] Direct attachment of the polymerase to the nanopore ensures that there is ample time for the polymer tags on the incoming nucleotide to be captured in the nanopore before completion of the DNA polymerase catalytic cycle. Polymerases like phi29 have less variable rates than exonucleases and therefore yield more consistent base identification in nanopore SBS. The measurements with PEG tags were performed in 150 mM KCl and 20 mM Hepes buffer at room temperature, [89] which is not ideal for polymerase reactions. The design and synthesis

of nucleotides tagged with modified oligonucleotides were optimized. These tags had structural modifications that created distinct current blockades, which were measured using an electronic chip-based array of nanopores embedded in lipid bilayer membranes. [89] The tags were attached to the terminal phosphate of 2'-deoxynucleoside-5'-hexaphosphates through Huisgen cycloaddition azide/alkyne coupling chemistry. [99] With these tagged nucleotides, Fuller et al. demonstrated continuous single-molecule electronic DNA sequencing with single-base resolution by biological nanopore SBS. The measurement of current was made during the polymerase catalytic cycle when the complementary tagged nucleotide was bound within the complex of the DNA polymerase, primer/template, and divalent metal cation, and it lasted until the completion of the polymerase catalytic step, with the release of the tagged polyphosphate product. After this product was released, the polymer tag was free to leave the pore, ending the blockade signal for that DNA synthesis step. [89] Each of the four tags had a distinctive structure that interacted with the narrowest constriction in the α HL channel, thereby decreasing the ionic current across the channel to different extents. [100,101]

Figure 8 Principle of nanopore SBS. (A) Single DNA polymerase molecule covalently attached to α HL nanopore along with a tertiary structure formed by a primer, template DNA, and tagged nucleotide with the polymerase. (B) Sequential capture and detection of tagged nucleotides as they produce nucleotide-specific current blockades.[89]

Four distinct transient current levels substantially below the open-pore current level were observed, thus indicating pore capture of the tags associated with each nucleotide during each cycle of the polymerase reaction. The bulkiest tag produced the lowest current, whereas an unmodified tag produced an intermediate current and the least bulky tags produced the highest currents. [89]

The Fuller et al. nanopore SBS experiments showed that the method can generate clear, sequence-dependent electronic signal streams at the single-molecule level in a continuous process that requires no addition or removal of reagents, even when

sequencing an array of multiple DNA templates. During these experiments, real-time single-molecule electronic DNA sequencing data with single-base resolution were obtained. Thus, the use of these polymer-tagged nucleotides should pave the way for new high-throughput sequencing methods.

4.1.2 DNA sequencing by synthesis using the MspA nanopore and quadromer map

Laszlo et al. have demonstrated a similar method for DNA sequencing with nanopores, which uses the MspA nanopore instead of α HL. In their experiments, a single MspA pore was established in a lipid bilayer. Figure 9 shows a cholesterol tag placed at the end of the fantail adaptor causing DNA to bind to the bilayer, thereby increasing the DNA concentration near the pore and increasing DNA-pore interactions. [102] Approximately four nucleotides determine the currents running through the MspA pore at any given time. [85,103] They then constructed a 256-nucleotide-long cyclical de Bruijn sequence [104] containing all possible combinations of the four nucleotides (quadromers) and broke them into eight separate strands. Phi29 DNA polymerase was used as a molecular motor to facilitate translocation of the sequence through the nanopore. Phi29 DNAP-based control of translocation resulted in two reads from each DNA molecule. The first was the 'unzipping,' in which one strand of the DNA moved 5' to 3' through the pore as the polymerase was forced to unzip the complementary strand. The second was 'synthesis,' in which the DNA moved 3' to 5' after the primer entered the DNAP's active site and the DNAP began synthesizing a complementary strand. [85] The group performed nanopore sequencing of all eight strands, averaging signals observed across multiple molecules of each strand to estimate the current level of the 256 quadromers,

thus obtaining a ‘quadromer map.’ This map was highly predictive of the ion current levels of previously unmeasured sequences in a library that the group constructed and that was derived from the genome of bacteriophage phi X 174. Overall, the predicted current levels from the de Bruijn sequence-based quadromer map strongly matched the observed current levels from nanopore sequencing of the phi X 174 DNA ($r = 0.9905$, 95% confidence boundaries, 0.9859–0.9936). The quadromer map was then tested with longer nanopore sequences, which aligned with high confidence levels, as well. [104]

Figure 9 (a) Method of adapting dsDNA for nanopore sequencing. The orange adaptor indicates a cholesterol tail inserted into the membrane, thus increasing the DNA capture rates. The green adaptors enable re-reading of the DNA using the DNAP’s synthesis mode. (b) The MspA nanopore is in blue, phi29 DNAP is in green and DNA is in orange. The voltage across the membrane drives a current through the pore, where DNA bases cause a signature ion current blockade. Phi29 DNAP passes DNA through the pore in single-nucleotide steps. (c–e) Raw data showing ion current changes as the DNA passes through the nanopore.[104]

The group then explored the potential of nanopore reads to facilitate hybrid assembly [105-107] by aligning short Illumina sequencing reads directly to the nanopore

ion current measurements. Because nanopore sequencing develops longer reads and higher throughput, such alignments may facilitate rapid and accurate sorting of short sequence reads into their proper order while requiring less than 30x coverage for accurate *de novo* genome assembly. The highest scoring alignment for all nanopore sequencing reads was to the phi X 174 genome. To systematically assess the power to detect single-base substitutions, the authors inserted various 'mock SNPs' into the reference genome of phi X 174 and successfully called 77.4% of the mock SNPs.[104] Overall, the nanopore sequencing using the quadromer map presented in Laszlo et al. can be unambiguously aligned to the phi X 174 reference genome and can be used as a viable algorithmic approach with respect to hybrid genome assembly and single-nucleotide polymorphism detection. The 4-nucleotide long recognition zone of MspA is advantageous in that it is short enough to have high current contrast, yet it is long enough to distinguish homopolymeric sections of two or three bases. Many of these analytical tools will apply to other nanopores with shorter constriction and may provide a foundation for nanopore sequencing for years to come. [104]

4.1.3 Limitations of SBS Technology

The technology of sequencing by synthesis using nanopores is not optimized, and can be further improved. For example, Fuller et al. believe that parameters that offer better resolved current blockade signatures, such as the synthesis of additional tagged nucleotides, may be optimized to yield better results. Additional factors that can be optimized include the improvement of reaction conditions and the testing of a variety of more efficient DNA polymerases. They have also investigated the decrease in the use of *SrCl₂* to moderate the progression of DNA synthesis. [89] Laszlo et al. stress that the

amplitude of ion current levels alone does not provide enough information for direct *de novo* sequencing in the absence of a reference for alignment and comparison. Furthermore, erratic and stochastic motion caused by the phi29 DNAP as it feeds the DNA through the pore contribute to errors in the nanopore sequencing system. They hypothesize that switching to a different enzyme, such as a helicase that steps along DNA monotonically and with less stochasticity, may markedly improve performance. [104] To improve the feasibility and future commercialization of nanopore sequencing, a method to confidently identify extended homopolymeric regions must be developed, and a more robust platform and parallelization must be achieved. [85] However, it has been shown that both α HL and MspA can discriminate DNA on a single-molecule level. The future is bright for this technology and may include possible applications in disease detection and drug screening.

5. Outlook

Considering the importance of a model membrane system and its applicability to the medical field, the advancement of this technology has been very slow to date. Biological protein nanopores are highly attractive engines for bio sensing applications because they are inexpensive to make and are highly reproducible and easily modified. An increasingly popular area in nanopore bio sensing is nucleic acid sequencing with high data rates, and long single-molecule reads already have been observed. [37] However, despite various examples of successful DNA translocation recordings and other protein detection, practical sensing devices have not yet arisen. [37] A significant limiting factor in the production of these devices is the membrane platform in which they are embedded.

Because an *in vitro* lipid bilayer was introduced in 1962, the lipid bilayer has not been successfully exploited for practical engineered applications, owing to its inherent fragility and short lifespan. Attempts to stabilize the membrane with hydrogels have yielded significant advances in lipid bilayer technology to develop a robust platform for bio sensing and sequencing applications. Myriad methods have been tested to improve the stability of a freestanding membrane. However, hydrogel encapsulation provides the most efficient means by which to stabilize the membrane structure while allowing electrical measurements to be collected without impediment. *In situ* hydrogel polymerization triggered by UV photoinitiation makes intimate contact with the membrane structure and shows significant improvement in membrane durability. Following this technique, a temperature-controlled hydro gelation technique has been explored for *in situ* polymerization and has led to a hydrogel-encapsulated membrane mounted on a modular chip, thus allowing it to be stored and transported. Although hydrogel-encapsulated lipid bilayers have substantially increased strength and durability, they have yet to reach a level of quality that establishes the durability of a high-throughput bio sensing systems that are able to endure storage and long-distance shipment. Additionally, conventional membranes must be made by hand and do not support full automation of membrane formation and data acquisition. To realize practical sensor applications using a biomimetic membrane platform, further improvements must be made.

Despite concerns regarding stability, automation, durability and ease of use, the outlook on artificial lipid bilayer membrane model structures is very promising. Techniques for automating membrane formation open doors for using the lipid bilayer platform for high-throughput ion channel screening. Kawano et al demonstrates

membranes that can withstand transportation and be used in an outdoor setting. Groups such as Fuller et al. and Laszlo et al. are also making advances in using the lipid bilayer in conjunction with biological nanopores as a sensing and sequencing tool with applications as broad as drug and genome screening and early cancer detection. Research in this field is growing, and with the vast number of groups collaborating to improve this technology and address its weaknesses, it is only a matter of time before the artificial lipid bilayer is recognized as the state-of-the-art, high-throughput bio sensing platform.

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